

SECANT NEWSLETTER

Security and privacy protection in Internet of Things devices

Issue #6

July 2024

Welcome to the 6th SECANT Newsletter!

We are pleased to announce the publication of the sixth issue of the SECANT newsletter.

SECANT is a 3-year Research and Innovation Action from 2021 to 2024 funded under Horizon 2020.

It kicked off in September 2021 and it gathers a consortium of 19 partners from 10 different countries including large ICT industries, SMEs, research institutes, 1 healthcare organization and 1 EU CERT.

With just 2 months away from the conclusion of the SECANT project, the Consortium remains focused on the innovations of the project!

Several milestones were achieved over the recent period, notably the successful integration of all primary modules under the SECANT platform and the finalization of the four Use Case demonstrators. These milestones are described in detail in this newsletter edition.

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PROJECT INFORMATION

SECANT: SECurity And privacy protection in IoT devices

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Overall budget: 6.567.958,75

EU contribution: 5.202.226,38

Coordinated by: NTT DATA SPAIN

STAY TUNED!

Stay updated on all our latest news, developments, research and general information regarding the SECANT project.

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Milestones

Since April 2024, SECANT has made significant progress in enhancing cybersecurity in complex network environments.

One of the most notable achievements has been the **successful integration of all primary modules under the SECANT platform**. This milestone ensures that all components work together providing comprehensive threat detection and privacy protection capabilities.

A major highlight of the project has been the **finalisation of four detailed Use Case (UC) demonstrators**, showcasing the capabilities of the integrated modules in practical scenarios. The demonstrators, led by SECANT's end users, covering **diverse use cases in healthcare highlight the versatility and effectiveness of SECANT**. This collaboration has been essential for testing and validating the system in operational environments, incorporating valuable feedback from actual users.

Starting the demos in operational environments is a critical step to verify the robustness of SECANT's solutions. These real-world tests will provide an authentic assessment of the system's performance under actual operating conditions, ensuring its reliability and effectiveness in practical applications. This hands-on approach will be crucial for addressing practical challenges and enhancing the system's overall functionality.

 USE CASE #2 Cyber security for connected medical devices and mobile applications Read More	
 USE CASE #4 Cyber Security Training Read More	

In conclusion, the progress made by the SECANT project underscores the **collaborative efforts of its development team and end-users**. The successful integration of all modules and the preparation of the UC demonstrations mark significant milestones, bringing SECANT closer to its goal of providing advanced SECURITY And privacy protection IN Internet of Things devices. As the project moves forward, the goal is to implement the four UC demonstrations. **Insights gained from these practical tests will be invaluable in further refining and perfecting the developed technologies.**

Looking ahead, SECANT will continue to advance, with ongoing iterations based on real-world feedback ensuring to bring innovation in cybersecurity.

Highlight: SECANT End-Users Workshop

On May 31, 2024, SECANT successfully concluded End-Users Workshop. The SECANT End-Users Workshop was attended by more than 40 participants both from the SECANT end-users partners and project partners from the consortium.

The main goal of this online workshop was to engage directly with our end-users' partners: Karolinska Institutet, Polaris Medical, and TIC Salut Social. By gathering these key stakeholders, we aimed to gather their insights and perspectives. The input received during the workshop is invaluable in finalising our developments and ensuring that the SECANT solution is not only effective but also aligned with the practical needs of our end-users.

The agenda of the Workshop included an overall overview of the SECANT project and thorough presentations of the 4 Use Cases of our project. Additionally, live demonstrations enriched the Q&A session and the interactive poll, which served as the final part of the workshop.

SECANT events participations

April
17

SECANT was represented at the **2nd ENISA Cybersecurity Policy Conference** which was held in Brussels, Belgium. Our project partner, DNSC, the national CERT of Romania attended the conference and discussed with representatives from other national authorities about the objectives of the SECANT project.

May
16-17

On 16-17 May 2024, SECANT was showcased at the **DefCamp Cluj Conference**, held in Romania. SECANT was disseminated via the DNSC's booth to over 400 participants from a diverse audience.

May
21-23

We are happy to announce that we have participated at the **IoT Solutions World Congress**, held in Barcelona, Spain. Our project partner, i2CAT, promoted SECANT and had the opportunity to discuss the project's vision and results with numerous attendees.

May
29-30

SECANT participated at the **Cybersec Europe 2024**, a cornerstone event for cybersecurity professionals. It was an incredible opportunity to showcase SECANT to over 3000 participants. Our project was hosted at DNSC booth, where we were delighted to engage with attendees and provide detailed answers to their questions.

2024 EuCNC & 6G Summit in Antwerp, Belgium: Our project partner, INFOLYSIS, effectively disseminated our marketing materials to a broad audience.

JUNE
participations

European Health Management Conference 2024: SECANT was represented by DNSC, which had discussions with interested people and disseminated marketing materials.

Synergies

SECANT Participation at the ELECTRON Dissemination Event

As part of its collaborative efforts with sister projects within the SecureCyber Cluster, SECANT took part in the ELECTRON dissemination event held on June 5th, 2024, at the CERTH premises in Thessaloniki, Greece.

The event was titled "Challenges and Solutions for Energy Cybersecurity: Lessons Learnt from ELECTRON & European Projects", and it provided insightful presentations from policy makers, cybersecurity experts, researchers, project representatives, and industrial stakeholders.

The discussions were mainly focused on modernizing infrastructure, enhancing cross-sector collaboration, adopting advanced security technologies, and fostering a culture of cybersecurity awareness.

From the SECANT's team, the Scientific and Technical Coordinator, ArnoIot Spyros from CERTH, delivered an enlightening presentation titled "Elevating Cybersecurity in Healthcare: The SECANT Approach", explaining the innovations and the ultimate goal of SECANT.

We extend our gratitude to the organisers from the ELECTRON project for the invitation to be part of this insightful event!

SECANT'S new collaboration with the Digital Health Uptake (DHU)

The SECANT project is pleased to announce a new collaboration as part of its networking and clustering activities with the Digital Health Uptake (DHU).

DHU is a European initiative that aims to facilitate the alignment of policies, strategies, instruments and activities to advance the uptake of digital health solutions and services in Europe. It is funded by the European Commission until October 2024 under the Digital Europe Programme. The work of DHU is grouped under three key aspects: RADAR, KNOWLEDGE COMMUNITY and ACCELERATOR.

SecureCyber Cluster – Enhancing Cybersecurity

SECANT project joined forces with other EU-funded projects to inaugurate the "SecureCyber Cluster – Enhancing Cybersecurity". This pioneering collaboration, officially launched online, unites various cybersecurity projects under a singular umbrella to bolster collective efforts against evolving threats.

Already engaged in joint seminars, workshops, webinars and the Horizon Results Booster programme, the cluster endeavours to spread awareness and propagate best practices in cybersecurity. The horizon anticipates further synergies throughout 2024, such as the Joint Cyber Threat Intelligence: Empowering IoT Security Workshop, mentioned above.

The SECANT project, among other EU H2020 projects such as IDUNN, KRAKEN, ELECTRON, CROSSCON, TRUSTaWARE, IRIS, SPATIAL, ERATOSTHENES, SENTINEL, and ARCADIAN-IoT, brings its unique perspective to fortify the cluster's initiatives.

The SECANT consortium

3 Large ICT industries

NTT DATA

THALES
Building a future we can all trust

SIMAVI
Software Imagination & Vision

9 SMEs
EIGHTBELLS
Independent Research & Consultancy

UBITECH
ubiquitous solutions

axon logic

**INFO
LYSIS**

**IANUS
TECHNOLOGIES**

EXALENS[®]

adrestia
Equipment & Research & Development

bi²S Ltd
Business and IoT
Integrated Solutions

5 research institutes and universities

**Karolinska
Institutet**

**Information
Technologies
Institute**

**UNIVERSITY OF
SURREY**

1 healthcare organization

1 European CERT

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